

SITE GPR	YEAR 11	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 62.6283 Max: 62.9635	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1386 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	Tabu Project
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In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 1732-1733	Photo Model: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No #:
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DEFINITION Square layer of rubble	Covered by <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1327	Fills <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:
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HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction	FORMATION PROCESS <input type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition
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INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are			SOIL/MATRIX clay 10% silt 85% sand 5%
Anthropoc <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery m <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tiles m <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Amphorae m <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	Geological <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) local f <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Travertine r <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Basalt f <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	Organic <input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal bones m <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth v <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive
			Compaction <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft
			Color <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)		Depth: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original
Northern Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Southern Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Western Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Eastern Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE	
Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts:
Is covered by: 1327	Covers: 1411, 1416
Is cut by:	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills:

OBSERVATIONS
The rocky fill was clearly distinguishable after the removal of some silty topsoil (SU 1327) and is also characteristic because of some reddish inclusions.

DESCRIPTION
Position within sector: South central in Area B 2011
Shape: almost square
 Δ 425 wom weight, Δ 427+ Δ 428 lamp, Δ 431 coin

For layers complete this section:
Surface (slope direction: visible inclusions): no slope, visible inclusions: rocks up to 25cm, reddish tufo fragments
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): no cluster, basalt pavement stone
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): stays the same, ca. 0.3m
Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commigled other (specify)

For cuts complete this section: Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight Cut sides: <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded Observations:	Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):
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For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

Fill within the walls of the room adjacent to room 1, consists of a large amount of tufo and basalt debris in a sandy, reddish brown soil. The fill contains little pottery and might in its upper part still be contaminated with soil from SU 1327.

Fill of a robbing activity? Or dump of quarry material? Some of the blocks we found were clearly quarried blocks from site but they did not seem to resemble collapse from the walls.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Charcoal

Size: biggest piece $\approx$ 2cm

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by CHM

on 13/7/11

Revised by CHM

on 20/7/11

PDFd by AMS

on 21/7/11

Entered by

on